

1 One Health Approach to Enhance Coronavirus
2 Surveillance in Bat-Livestock-Human Interface in Bat
3 Guano Farming Community

4 Felicia Nutter², Jennifer Peterson⁶, Thavry Hoem⁷, Theara Teng¹,
5 Ratana Chhan¹, Dou Sok¹, Chanthy Srey¹, Bunna Chea³, Bruno M. Ghersi⁵,
6 Jeffrey C. Mariner², Tristan Burgess⁴, Malen Ken^{1*}

7
8 **1** Tetra Tech ARD, STOP Spillover, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

9 **2** Cummings School of Veterinary Medicine, Tufts University, North Grafton,
10 MA, USA

11 **3** Center for Wildlife Studies, South Freeport, ME 04097 USA

12 **4** Royal University of Agriculture, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

13 **5** One Health Institute, School of Veterinary Medicine, UCDAVIS

14 **6** Tetra Tech ARD, Burlington, Vermont, USA

15 **7** Institut Pasteur du Cambodge, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

16 **8** National Animal Health and Production Research Institute, Phnom Penh,
17 Cambodia

18 * Correspondence author: kenmalen18@gmail.com

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Abstract

The increasing use of bat guano as a fertilizer in Cambodia's agricultural sector has raised concerns about zoonotic disease transmission, particularly coronaviruses, at the bat-livestock-human interface. This study employs a One Health approach to enhance coronavirus surveillance within bat guano farming communities in Kampong Cham province. By integrating human, animal, and environmental health expertise, the surveillance system aims to detect potential zoonotic spillover events. Participatory Syndromic Surveillance (PSS) was conducted, involving community engagement and sample collection from humans, livestock, and bats. Laboratory analyses revealed the presence of various coronaviruses across different species. In humans, SARS-CoV-2 was detected in 17 individuals, while beta coronavirus HKU1 was identified in one case. Among livestock, bovine coronavirus was found in one cow, and avian coronavirus was detected in five chickens. Environmental samples from bat guano farms showed the presence of bat-associated alphacoronaviruses in four samples. The overall positivity rate for coronaviruses in bat guano samples was 2.08%. These findings underscore the importance of a One Health framework in identifying and mitigating zoonotic risks. The surveillance system demonstrated its capability to detect simultaneous coronavirus infections across species, highlighting the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health. This approach provides a valuable model for early

43 detection and prevention of zoonotic diseases, contributing to public health
44 safety in high-risk interfaces.

45 **Author summary**

46 Zoonotic diseases, transmitted between animals and humans, pose a growing
47 threat to public health, especially in vulnerable communities. Interactions
48 between humans, livestock, and wildlife increase the risk of disease
49 transmission. Despite the significant health and economic burden, control
50 strategies often rely solely on government efforts. To address this, our study
51 investigated the presence of coronaviruses and assessed the risks faced by
52 exposed individuals. By adopting a One Health approach, which integrates
53 human and animal health, we aim to develop comprehensive, community-
54 based strategies for zoonotic disease surveillance and control at the bat-
55 livestock-human interface.

56 **Introduction**

57 The shift towards alternative sources of fertilizer has significantly increased the
58 value and popularity of bat guano in Cambodia's agricultural sector. Renowned
59 for its rich nutrient content, bat guano commands a high price, making it a viable
60 source of livelihood for communities. In Kampong Cham province, particularly
61 in Kang Meas, artificial bat roosts have been constructed to facilitate bat guano
62 'farming'. This initiative spans three villages including Varint 1, Varint 2, and
63 Varint 3 encompassing 17 bat guano farms. These villages comprise 654

64 households, with a total population of 2,368, according to the annual report of
65 Khchau commune administration of Kang Meas district [1].

66 Bats are known reservoirs for a range of pathogens, including Rabies, Nipah
67 Virus and coronaviruses such as SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 [2].

68 While viruses of known public health significance have not previously been
69 detected in the bats residing on bat guano farms, only a limited amount of
70 sampling has investigated this question. There remains a real possibility that
71 such pathogens exist at certain times or at low prevalence but have so far gone
72 undetected. Close proximity and frequent contact between humans, livestock,
73 and bats on guano farms provide the other essential preconditions for zoonotic
74 disease transmission. Guano harvesters handle guano regularly, and prior to
75 beginning STOP Spillover interventions, we documented low levels of risk
76 perception and little or no use of PPE [3]. Food and surface sampling at guano
77 farms also documented bat-associated alphacoronaviruses on household surfaces
78 and avian coronaviruses (Infectious Bronchitis Virus) on food surfaces,
79 presumably carried there either by poultry entering the home or by the residents
80 themselves. This demonstrated the clear possibility of a take-home pathway for
81 coronaviruses, and potentially other pathogens from guano farms into the home
82 in areas where all family members may be at risk of exposure.

83 While a specific link between bat exposure and respiratory diseases, (potentially
84 including those caused by coronaviruses), in guano farming communities has not
85 been demonstrated, robust disease surveillance is essential for building a clear
86 understanding of these risks. By gathering real-time data, we can better prevent

87 disease outbreaks, manage spillover events, and establish effective early warning
88 systems while refining our knowledge of high-risk interfaces. It has proven very
89 difficult to establish epidemiological links between pathogens which occur at
90 low prevalence or incidence and the settings in which spillover occurs [4], and
91 only with sustained interface-level surveillance can such links be established [5].
92 In the realm of public health, traditional disease surveillance methods, which
93 rely on confirmed cases identified through laboratory testing, often face
94 limitations due to limited reach. Syndromic surveillance too, can be hampered by
95 lack of reporting, inadequate community engagement or conflict with health-
96 seeking behaviors. Cambodia has a developed syndromic surveillance system
97 linked to laboratory testing targeting Severe Acute Respiratory Illness (SARI)
98 and Influenza Like illness (ILI) based on public health facilities including the
99 community health center in Khchau commune. The community assessment
100 conducted by STOP Spillover found, however, that about 60-65% of participants
101 interviewed in the bat guano farming communities preferred to seek treatment
102 with private clinics rather than the community health center. This means the
103 majority of potential cases may not even be available for detection by the
104 existing surveillance program [6]. Bats are effective disease carriers due to their
105 long lifespan, diverse diet, and ability to fly, which brings them into close
106 contact with humans and domestic animals [7]. The risk of the zoonotic spillover
107 risk at bat guano farming remains unknown. One Health surveillance describes
108 the systematic collection, validation, analysis, interpretation of data and
109 dissemination of information collected on humans, animals and the environment

110 to inform decisions for more effective, evidence- and system-based health
111 interventions [8]. The study on bats identified Bat were classified into two main
112 suborders 1,116 species in 18 families belonging to 2 suborders including
113 Microchiroptera and Megachiroptera [9]. Different species of bat have different
114 risk factors and levels of risk to humans. Bat guano farming is a type of bat
115 species living in artificial roost built from palm leaves which is popular in
116 Cambodia using organic fertilizer and is a lucrative livelihood for agriculture and
117 fruit plantation in Cambodia like durian and acting as natural pest controller
118 [10,11].

119 Along with the great benefit of the bat, this species plays a critical role as a
120 host for potential viral spillover. A bat guano farm study by USAID, STOP
121 Spillover, identified the lesser Asiatic yellow bat (*Scotophilus kuhlii*) is a
122 species of vesper batis a predominant bat species in artificial bat roost in Bat
123 guano farming community in Cambodia [12]. The PREDICT 2 identified
124 coronavirus in human and domestic animals was noteworthy, as these viruses
125 are known to affect the health and productivity of these animals. However,
126 the spillover was not identified as the source of the bat yet. In addition, a
127 significant percentage of residents in Kang Meas districts, Kampong Cham
128 province, Cambodia engage in risky behaviors related to water and food
129 safety. In Kang Meas, 59% share water sources with animals, and 27%
130 consume food contaminated by animal feces [13]. This study aims to identify
131 the possibility of cross-species transmission of coronaviruses from
132 *Scotophilus kuhlii* bat and identify the level of risk to human health in bat

133 guano farming communities, testing One Health approach to strengthening
134 the surveillance on zoonotic diseases such as coronavirus and risk reduction
135 intervention at interface level. Development of a subnational interface-level
136 of One Health surveillance team will increase detection and diagnosis of
137 syndromes of concern to prevent zoonotic spillover.

138 **Materials and methods**

139 **Establishment of One Health Design, Research and** 140 **Mentoring (OH-DReaM) working group**

141 A surveillance team was first convened in October 2022 to conduct Participatory
142 Syndromic Surveillance (PSS) within bat guano farming communities. The
143 interdisciplinary group comprised 16 personnel from multiple government
144 agencies in One Health framework from Cambodia Communicable Diseases
145 Control (CCDC) department, General Directorate of Animal Health and
146 Production (GDAHP), National Animal Health and Production Research
147 Institute (NAHPRI), Ministry of Environment (MoE), Provincial Health
148 Department (PHD), Provincial Department of Agriculture, Forestry and
149 Fisheries (PDAFF), Health Operational District (OD), Referral Hospital (RH),
150 and Health Centers (HCs), to facilitate a One Health (OH) approach for specific
151 coronaviruses surveillance. The team underwent rigorous training in using
152 participatory epidemiology tools, participatory syndromic surveillance
153 implementation protocols, sample collection technique, and biosafety procedures

154 to prepare for the pilot program. A strong collaboration with the two laboratories
155 Institut Pasteur du Cambodge (IPC) and National Animal health and Production
156 Research Institute (NAHPRI) played a critical role in delivering laboratory
157 analytical services to the surveillance team.

158 **Case Definition and sample selection criteria**

159 This program of community engagement and trust building plays an important
160 role in case detection using first-hand information to report the event on the
161 ground. One Health approach used participatory epidemiology tools by
162 implementation proceeded using an agreed-upon case definition of Febrile
163 Respiratory Illness (FRI). The case definition for FRI was established as follows:
164 The mandatory symptom is Fever exceeding 38°C and at least two of other
165 symptoms (mucus production, sore throat, cough, muscle pain, shortness of
166 breath).

167 The team collected nasopharyngeal swabs from individuals presenting with
168 respiratory symptoms, as well as from up to two other members of the same
169 household. This targeted sampling approach aimed to identify potential cases
170 and contacts within the community, focusing on the upper respiratory tract
171 where coronaviruses commonly replicate. The sentinel surveillance team was
172 stationed at the Khchau Health Center, prepared to collect samples from
173 participants as they arrived.

174 Each human syndromic case also triggered livestock sampling. For each case,
175 oral and rectal/cloacal swabs were obtained from up to five poultry (chicken,
176 duck) and nasal and rectal swabs were collected from two mammalian livestock

177 animals (cow, buffalo, horse and pig) to capture potential viral presence in both
178 the respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts. Additionally, non-invasive
179 environmental samples of bat feces and urine were gathered. Eight bat fecal
180 samples and four bat urine samples were collected per case detection from the
181 nearest bat guano farm to each index case up to a maximum of 100m distance
182 from their home.

183 **Laboratory testing**

184 Two laboratories processed the respective sample types in accordance with the
185 division of responsibilities agreed with the competent ministries (Figure 1). All
186 human samples were tested at IPC, while all animal-origin samples (including
187 guano) were tested at NAHPRI. Similar protocols were used by the two
188 laboratories, but there were some important differences, highlighted below.

189 All nucleic acid extractions were conducted utilizing a commercial Qiagen kit,
190 QIAamp™ Viral RNA mini kit (QIAamp Viral RNA Kits | Viral RNA Isolation |
191 QIAGEN, no date). Samples were pooled at the laboratory pre-extraction into
192 five-member groups for primary screening. Positive pools were subsequently
193 subjected to de-pooling, starting from individual RNA extraction. For the initial
194 cDNA synthesis step, a 25 µL reaction mixture was prepared using the
195 SuperScript™ II First-Strand Synthesis SuperMix (Thermo Scientific, Waltham,
196 MA, USA) kit according to the manufacturer's standard protocol unless
197 otherwise stated. This mixture consisted of 10 µL RNA and 1 µL of random
198 hexamers then were amplified through ThermoFisher Veriti™ 96 well
199 thermocycler for 90 mins. A 23 µL PCR master mix was prepared containing 0.1

200 μ L Invitrogen™ Platinum™ Taq DNA Polymerase, 0.75 μ L MgCl₂, 2.5 μ L 1X
 201 PCR buffer, and 0.5 μ L of each primer. Two microliters of cDNA product were
 202 added to the master mix. PCR amplification, targeting either reverse
 203 transcription or duplicate target sequences, was performed using a ThermoFisher
 204 Veriti™ 96-well thermocycler [14] (see Domínguez et al., 2007 for additional
 205 protocol detail). IPC deployed a two-step hemi-nested amplification protocol. In
 206 the first step, a standard RT-PCR assay is performed using primers targeting a
 207 ~602bp region of the RdRp gene. If the first PCR assay is negative, a second
 208 hemi-nested PCR is performed using the product from reaction one as the
 209 template in reaction two to increase the sensitivity of the detection. The second
 210 PCR uses the same forward primer as the first PCR, but a different reverse
 211 primer (Table 1). This primer pair yields a shorter amplicon (23 nt) but allows
 212 for detection of lower levels of viral RNA.
 213 NAHPRI employs a different primer set targeting a ~440-bp region of the RdRp
 214 gene [15] (Table 2) (see Lacroix et al., 2020 for additional protocol detail).

215 **Table 1. Primers used for Pan-CoV conventional PCR at IPC laboratory.**

Primers		Sequence
<i>Step1</i>	Forward	5'-GGTTGGGACTATCCTAAGTGTGA-3'
	Reverse	5'-CCATCATCAGATAGAATCATCAT-3'
<i>Step2</i>	Forward	5'-GGTTGGGACTATCCTAAGTGTGA-3'
	Reverse	5'-ATCAGATAGAATCATCATAGAGA-3'

216 **Table 2. Primers used for Pan-CoV conventional PCR at NAHPRI laboratory.**

Primers		Sequence
<i>Step1</i>	Forward	5'-GGTTGGGACTATCCTAAGTGTGA-3'
	Reverse	5'-GGTTGGGACTATCCTAAGTGTGA-3'

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218 PCR products were visualized using gel electrophoresis on a Mupid-exU (Takara
219 Bio Inc. Kusatsu, Shiga, Japan). Gels were imaged and analyzed using a GelDox
220 (Bio Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) imaging system. Positive PCR products were
221 sequenced in both directions by direct Sanger sequencing a commercial facility
222 (Macrogen, Inc., Seoul, Republic of Korea).

223 **Test result analysis**

224 Processing and basic analyses of anonymized participant data was performed
225 using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Inc Redmond, WA, USA). Sequences were
226 aligned using GenBank and Geneious Prime (Biomatters, Auckland, NZ).
227 Sequences were compared to the nearest matching sequences contained in
228 GenBank using the BLAST tool. A phylogenetic tree based on the RNA
229 sequences was constructed using the Neighbor-Joining method with 500
230 bootstrap replicates using Geneious Prime.

231 **Consultative meeting**

232 Agreement and approval from the competent ministries and government
233 agencies was essential to providing timely results-sharing for participants. To
234 address this issue, a series of consultative meetings with participating
235 government partners and laboratories (CCDC, GDAHP, NAHPRI and IPC) was

236 conducted virtually and in person to build consensus on protocols for rapid
237 sharing of laboratory test results with the communities, to discuss the laboratory
238 testing protocols and to finalize approvals for distribution of surveillance
239 findings, both to individual patients and to the community in general.

242 **Ethics statement**

243 The surveillance program study was approved by the National Ethics Committee
244 of Health Research. The reference number reference is 262 NECHR, study
245 protocol version No1, dated 3rd June 2023. Animal handling and sampling
246 activities were approved by the Tufts University IACUC (protocol #G2021-75)
247 for the STOP Spillover project. This program received all necessary approvals
248 from the General Directorate of Animal Health and production of the Ministry of
249 Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (MAFF). The surveillance program was a
250 Public Health Surveillance program - an activity deemed not to be researched
251 under the 2018 HHS guidance (US Department of Health and Human Services
252 2018). The program was implemented by the relevant ministries in Cambodia
253 with support from STOP Spillover and was therefore not subject to IRB review.

254 **Fig 1. One Health surveillance on coronavirus implementation process.**

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256 descriptions instead of using subfigure commands.

257 **Results**

Case reporting & sampling

A total of 180 individuals interviewed in the PSS, including 85 adult females and 20 girls. Ninety percent of reported cases were brought to the attention of community health workers or local leaders. When interviewed, participants revealed that they did not seek healthcare at health centers. Instead, they opted for treatment from commune health workers or private clinics due to the significant distance to health centers and these facilities were easier to access.

Fig 2. A proportion of the cases and family members presenting with different symptoms in the bat guano farming community in the three rounds of one health surveillance. During the three surveillance trips, the one health surveillance team detected a total of 45 syndromic cases from 45 households. Forty-five participants consented to sample collection. A further consented 53 participants were sampled as household members of case detections. The most reported symptoms were Cough (58%) and Fever (56%).

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Fig 3. A proportion of the cases and family members presenting with different symptoms in the bat guano farming community in the three rounds of one health surveillance. Tracing back these syndromic cases to their households triggered sampling of a further 129 chickens, 32 ducks, and 59 cows across the 28 consenting households. Additionally, 104 bat guano and 39 bat urine samples were collected from eight bat guano farms linked to reported cases by proximity. (a) Map showing the location of coronavirus infected cases' household and non-infected cases household. (b) Map showing the sampled livestock household and sampled bat guano farm.

Fig 4. A comparison of the cases and family members detected in one health surveillance with confirmed laboratory test results. The number of cases detected and confirmed positive cases from laboratory results were significantly different.

Table 1. Overview of laboratory data that were presented in each species case.

Species	Type of samples	No. of samples	Positive	GenBank Match	Percent Identity (%)
<i>Human^a</i>	Nasopharyngeal swab	98	1	Beta coronavirus HKU1 SC2628	100
			17	Beta coronavirus	99.34 - 100

				Covid 19	
<i>Cow^b</i>	Nasal swab	29	1	Bovine coronavirus isolate PL/2014/Op1/III/BCoV	99.52
	Rectal swab	29	0	-	-
<i>Chicken^b</i>	Cloacal swab	65	1	Avian coronavirus isolate AvCoV/Duck/Laos/LAO11_A_075/2011	98.62
	Oral swab	65	4	Gammacoronavirus sp. isolate AvCoV/chicken/Vietnam	99.52 - 100
<i>Duck^b</i>	Cloacal swab	16	0	-	-
	Oral swab	16	0	-	98.62
<i>Bat^b</i>	Environmental feces	96	1	Scotophilus bat coronavirus Alphacoronavirus sp. strain	100
			4	Alphacoronavirus sp. strain	99.52 - 100

				VZ_AlphaCoV_1684	
				5_47	
	Urine swab	47	0	-	-

296 ^a the specimen samples were tested at IPC laboratory. ^b the specimen samples were tested at NAHPRI
297 laboratory.

299 **Fig 5. The phylogenetic tree of coronavirus strain detected in bat guano**

300 **farming community.** Three rounds of One Health surveillance were conducted.
301 In the first round (January), during the juvenile bat season, one positive case was
302 detected in a human. This sample tested positive for Coronavirus HKU1. Other
303 samples collected from the homes of human cases returned positive results also
304 including one from chickens (Infectious Bronchitis Virus - a Gamma
305 coronavirus), and one from bat guano/urine (bat-associated alphacoronaviruses).
306 The second round (March), coinciding with early to mid-gestation in bats,
307 yielded no positive lab results, even though a slightly greater number of
308 syndromic cases were found (15 vs 11 in round 1). Round 3(June), during the
309 lactation period for the bats, showed a notable increase in positive lab results -
310 with 17 positive test results from 19 human patients. All 17 human positives
311 were found to SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19). At the same time four chickens were
312 positive for Infectious Bronchitis Virus, one cow tested positive for bovine
313 coronavirus and three bat guano samples were positive for bat-associated
314 alphacoronaviruses.

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Discussion

In this study, fostering collaboration among human, animal, and environmental health experts, has enabled effective coronavirus surveillance. This collaborative effort has led to valuable insights, including the detection of coronaviruses in various species and environmental samples, such as humans, livestock, and bats. The presence of coronavirus in these samples highlights the importance of One Health in identifying potential sources of zoonotic infections and timely implementation of control measures, reducing the risk of outbreaks. This surveillance system has also demonstrated its ability to detect simultaneous coronavirus infections in human patients and animals at their households. The study we identified positive coronavirus in cows from the same household where the human was also detected positive coronavirus for SARS-CoV2., and this the cattle sample virus was identified as Bovine Coronavirus (BCoV) which has been studied and known as a viral strain that has is a well-known pathogen of cattle, but also has the potential to be transmitted to humans. Bovine coronavirus (BCoV) has caused widespread outbreaks on five continents, often manifesting as intestinal infections and diarrhea in cattle. While primarily affecting livestock, BCoV may also pose a potential risk to human biosafety health, necessitating rigorous monitoring and preventive measures [16,17]. In this instance it was not a spillover of BCoV into humans that was detected, but rather a simultaneous detection of an unrelated virus in the human patient. Nonetheless this demonstrates the performance of the system in detecting simultaneous

338 coronavirus infections in humans and animals. It is worth noting that lab positive
339 human cases were detected simultaneously with lab positive alphacoronaviruses
340 on the nearest bat guano farm.

341 From The 96 bat guano samples collected, there was a prevalence that showed
342 an overall positivity rate of 2.08% of Coronaviridae sp. isolate 75-55-L06-R2-
343 CoV-BAT-VN which is an alphacoronavirus lineage. These findings were not
344 different from the previous on bat farm of STOP Spillover which identified only
345 one dominant species of bat called *Scotophilus kuhlii* [18]. The sequence result
346 showed the different strain of coronavirus in humans, thus showing that there is
347 no association of viral transmission between human and bat.

348 A collaborative effort between the NAHPRI and CCDC with support from IPC
349 and STOP Spillover simultaneously assessed the presence of coronaviruses in
350 humans, animals and environmental samples in bat guano farming communities.
351 The findings, which were reviewed and approved by the government and health
352 authorities, revealed no immediate public health risk. More importantly,
353 however, the system demonstrated an ability to significant numbers of FRI cases
354 that would not be accessible to the traditional public health surveillance systems,
355 to detect pathogenic coronaviruses including SARS-CoV2 in these patients and
356 document simultaneous viral shedding by humans and domestic animals. The
357 system therefore can detect the conditions expected of a hypothetical future
358 zoonotic coronavirus spillover and is therefore a valuable model for deployment
359 in high-risk interfaces in Cambodia and elsewhere in the world.

Conclusion

OH, institutionalization was highly effective in breaking down perceptions of mistrust against external researchers and government officials. Risk is dependent on the presence of hazards and exposure. Although there is exposure to bats on bat guano farms, repeated studies have not documented the presence of major hazards in the bats farmed in artificial and tree roots in Southeast Asia. The failure to identify hazards any more severe than those found in other species of livestock suggests that the level of risk posed on guano farm collection is similar to that of other forms of animal agriculture. The thread of coronavirus mutation is always present. Through a participatory approach to the zoonotic surveillance, guano producers themselves are the first actor to inform the health authority of possible future spillover. In addition, self-protective measures such as hygiene practice and using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) should be employed as in all animal agriculture. These build a foundation to deal with future outbreak rapidly, effectively at local level.

Supporting information

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